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THE SCHOOLING OF CHILDREN LEFT-BEHIND BY THE MIGRATION OF PARENTS ALONG THE BURKINA FASO - IVORY COAST CORRIDOR: A SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC VIEW

LA SCOLARITÉ DES ENFANTS RESTÉS AU PAYS PAR LA MIGRATION DES PARENTS DANS LE CORRIDOR BURKINA FASO - CÔTE D'IVOIRE : UNE VUE SOCIO-DÉMOGRAPHIQUE

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Abstract.

Migration, a global phenomenon is generally practiced in search of livelihood for improved living conditions. This historic phenomenon in the Burkina Faso – Ivory Coast corridor also affects the lives of other people beyond just migrants. These include children who remain in the country, where at least one biological parent is migrating. This situation can have major effects on the psychological and emotional protection, schooling and health of these children who remain in the country. This article establishes a comparison between the level of schooling of children from households where one or both biological parents have migrated along the Burkina Faso-Côte d'Ivoire corridor to that of children from other households. To achieve this, empirical data were collected in November 2020 in several localities in Burkina Faso following a quantitative approach. The analysis of primary and original data collected in the migrants' areas of origin shows that a certain number of characteristics of the households to which the children remaining in the country belong negatively affect their schooling. These characteristics include the main occupation of the head of household, the place of residence of the household, the age and marital status of the head of household. However, the sex of the head of household is not a significant factor. This educational performance of children can be explained by the fact that in the absence of biological parents, children who remain in the country do not benefit from adequate supervision. The data show that the impact on schooling is greater when the father has migrated (92% do not attend school at all), less significant when only the mother has migrated (59%), compared to both parents (76%). These results allow more in-depth investigations into the understanding of the paradigm of children left behind.

Keywords: migration, schooling, children left behind, Burkina Faso – Ivory Coast Corridor.

Résumé

La migration, un phénomène mondial est pratiqué généralement à la recherche de moyens de subsistance pour une amélioration des conditions de vie. Ce phénomène historique dans le couloir Burkina Faso – Côte d'Ivoire affecte également la vie d'autres personnes au-delà des seuls migrants. Il s'agit notamment des enfants restés au pays, dont au moins un des parents biologiques est en migration. Cette situation peut avoir des effets majeurs sur la protection psychologique et affective, la scolarisation ainsi que la santé de ces enfants restés au pays.

Cet article établit une comparaison entre le niveau de scolarisation des enfants des ménages dont l'un des parents ou les deux parents biologiques ont migré le long du corridor Burkina Faso-Côte d'Ivoire à celui des enfants des autres ménages. Pour y arriver, des données empiriques ont été collectées en novembre 2020 dans plusieurs localités du Burkina Faso suivant une approche quantitative.

L'analyse des données primaires et originales collectées dans les zones d'origine des migrants, montre qu'un certain nombre de caractéristiques des ménages auxquels appartiennent les enfants restés au pays affectent négativement leur scolarisation. Ces caractéristiques sont entre autres l'occupation principale du chef de ménage, le lieu de résidence du ménage, l'âge et l'état matrimonial du chef de ménage. Cependant le sexe du chef de ménage n'est pas un facteur significatif. Ce résultat scolaire des enfants peut s'expliquer par le fait qu'en l'absence de parents biologiques, les enfants restés au pays ne bénéficient pas d'un encadrement adéquat. Les données montrent que l'impact sur la scolarisation est plus important lorsque le père a migré (92%

ne fréquentent pas du tout l'école), moins important lorsque seule la mère a migré (59%), par rapport aux deux parents (76%). Ces résultats autorisent des investigations plus approfondies de la compréhension du paradigme des enfants restés au pays.

Mots clés : migration, scolarisation, enfants laissés pour compte, Corridor Burkina Faso - Côte d'Ivoire.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of migration is affirmed by the establishment of major institutions dealing with the issue, and proven by the productions that follow, especially since migration paradigms are diverse and varied. They associate the interrelationships between population displacement and migration motives. These paradigms define the typology of migration and look at the place of children in migration, remittances, and their allocation as well as the impacts on areas of departure and destination. Thus, since the year 2000, IOM is in 2020, its 10th production of the “State of World Migration” report. The 2020 report reveals the major changes that have affected migration in recent years. These include the signing of global compacts on climate change and mass international displacement, notably the “Global Compact on Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration” and the “Global Compact on Refugees”. Recently, discussions have been underway for the adoption of a pact on COVID-19. From this report, statistics reveal 272 million international migrants worldwide, 52% of whom are men. The majority, 74%, are between the ages of 20 and 64. The estimated proportion of children among international migrants is 13.9%. Migrant workers number about 164 million. International remittances have reached US \$689 billion. Thus, globalization has opened up new migration trajectories that are now less dependent on colonial pasts (C. W. DE WENDEN, 2002, p. 24; M. HARZOUNE, 2022¹). Nowadays, there are several types of migrant trajectories and demographic profiles (male, female, child, youth, adult and old). Depending on the profile, migrants are affected differently according to the obstacles encountered and the level of vulnerability. Burkina Faso is a developing country, characterized by 45.3% of the population under 15 years old, while 64.2% of the population is under 24 years old and 77.9% is under 35 years old according to the preliminary results of the 5th General Census of Population and Housing 2019 (INSD, 2020 p. 44). Due to high levels of poverty, limited employment opportunities, and its geographical position, the country has long been a centre for migration. For decades, it has experienced high rates of emigration, particularly to Ivory Coast. At the same time, it is a country of immigration (B.H. DABIRE et al, 2009 p. 63). The impact of this migration on households and on national development is poorly understood. The different dimensions of migration, namely emigration, remittances, return migration, and immigration, are likely to have both positive and negative impacts on household welfare and key sectors of the Burkinabe economy. Indeed, migrants who move with their children seem to expose their offspring's to protection, access to education and health care risks, compared to families whose parents do not migrate. It is in this sense that the notion of equality among children is perceived within the framework of the MIDEQ (*Migration for Development and Equality*) project, whose axis 2 (Work Package 2) is entitled “Inequalities related to childhood in migration situation”. In the literature, the family environment has an influence on children's chances of schooling (J-F KOBIANE, 2001 p. 37; B. C. LLOYD et A. K. BLANC, 1996 p. 267; R. MARCOUX, 1995 p. 661; M. PILON, 1995 p.707). Hence, it is valid to ask the question of whether this family environment has an influence on the schooling chances of left-behind children. This is what led to the present study, which focuses on the schooling of children left behind in the context of migration in the Burkina Faso-Ivory Coast corridor. This study takes stock of the schooling of Burkinabe children whose parents have migrated to the Ivory Coast. In other words, the

¹ <https://www.histoire-immigration.fr/les-migrations/la-mondialisation-accelere-t-elle-les-migrations> [consulted on 05/10/2023].

objective of this paper is to explore the link between family characteristics and the schooling of left-behind children.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sampling

In order to provide information on the schooling of children left behind, a household survey was conducted. This is a quantitative survey of households. Thus, the target groups are made up of households, emigrants from the household in Ivory Coast, migrants returning from Ivory Coast, and children aged between 5 and 17 years. The following are considered eligible households

- Households with no international migration experience (only the household questionnaire was administered)
- Households with migration experience in Ivory Coast (in addition to the household questionnaire, all emigrants in Ivory Coast and all immigrants or returnees from Ivory Coast who meet the conditions described above were surveyed). This survey is not national for security reasons and because of the rarity of child migration. It covers four regions: The South West region (capital Gaoua), the West Center (capital Koudougou), the Central Board (capital Ziniar'e) and the East-Center region (capital Tenkodogo)

Map 1: Location of the study regions

These regions were chosen on the basis of data from 2019, the General Population and Housing Census (RGPH 2019). Indeed, these regions record the highest concentrations of international migration. In addition to these four regions, the country's two largest cities, Ouagadougou in the Centre region and Bobo-Dioulasso in the Hauts-Bassins region, were also selected for the survey.

The geographical area covered by the survey was stratified into three strata. The first includes the two major cities of Burkina Faso (Ouagadougou and Bobo Dioulasso), the second consists

of the secondary cities, i.e., the capitals of the four regions (Gaoua, Koudougou, Ziniar'e, Tenkodogo), and the third one, the rural areas of these four regions. This stratification can be explained by the fact that the urban or rural areas of residence is very important for migration in Burkina Faso.

Map 2: Distribution of Enumeration Areas by residence (urban)

Map 3: Distribution of Enumeration Areas by residence (rural)

The sampling is intended to be probability-based as this method gives each unit a chance to be drawn. The sampling frame of the last general population and housing census of 2019 provided by the INSD was used to calculate the sample size. The sampling frame generally used for surveys in Burkina Faso is that of the enumeration zones (EZ) from the most recent general population and housing census conducted by the National Institute of Statistics and Demography (INSD), in this case, the 2019 census. This is a geographic database that consists of a fine partition of the country into operational geographic census zones of about 2000 inhabitants each or an average of 400 households. At the time of the last census in 2019, Burkina Faso had 24,000 EZ; it is this file that served as the sampling frame. For the calculation of the sample size, the classic formula is used.

$$n = \frac{z_{\alpha/2}^2 \times P \times (1 - P)}{E^2} \times Deff \times (1 + T)$$

Where:

- n=sample size
- P=prevalence of emigration to Ivory Coast E^2 =margins of error
- Deff=Cluster effect
- T=non-response rate

To estimate the sample size, the prevalence of emigration in the Ivory Coast is considered a variable of interest. In the absence of updated statistics on migration in Burkina Faso, the prevalence of migration was set at 50% and assuming 95% confidence interval $z_{\alpha/2}$ equal to 1.96, 5% margin of error and 10% non-response rate. This results in an approximate minimum size of 423 without the cluster effect. In the various surveys conducted in Burkina Faso, the value of the cluster effect varies between 1.5 and 3. To take this into account in the sample calculation, the value of 2 was retained. Thus, the final sample size increased to 423×2 , equal to 846 emigrants in the Ivory Coast.

Multiple Component Analysis

The Multiple Correspondences Analysis (MCA) method allows the study of the association between at least two qualitative variables. This method, like principal component analysis (PCA), is applied to a table of individual*variable data. It is based on the construction of the complete disjunctive table, which is one of the preliminary steps for its implementation. To do this, the p qualitative variables are broken down into p disjunctive tables Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_p , composed of as many columns as there are modalities for each of the variables. Each time a modality m of the j^{th} variable corresponds to individual i , we assign 1 to $Z_j(i, m)$. The other values of Z_j are zero. The p disjunctive tables are then concatenated into a complete disjunctive table. From the complete disjunctive table, the coordinates of the categorical variable modalities are calculated, as well as the coordinates of the observations in a representation space that is optimal for the inertia criterion. In the case of the Multiple Correspondence Analyses, we show that the inertia is equal to the average number of modalities minus one. It, therefore does not depend on solely on the association between the variables. This adjustment makes it possible to have higher and more informative percentages for the representation axes. Multiple Correspondence Analyses is used in this study to see the association between the socio-demographic characteristics of the households to which the children left behind belong and their level of education.

RESULTS

The results are presented in two stages. The first step concerns the simple descriptive analysis and the second step concerns the multidimensional analysis.

Descriptive analysis

A total of 6044 households were surveyed, 85.6% of which were headed by men and 14.4% by women. Of the 6044 households surveyed, 3413 had at least one member under the age of 18. Of the 3413 households that have a member under the age of 18, 86% of households are headed by men and 14% by women.

In total, 8518 children were identified, 52% of whom were boys and 48% girls. Of the 8518 children, 8% (682) are children who have at least one parent who has migrated. Of all the left behind children identified, 52% are boys and 48% are girls.

Types of left behind by gender

Gender	Migrants		
	Mother	Father	Both Parents
Male	8.7%	68.2%	23.1%
Female	9.8%	68.8%	21.4%
Total	9.2%	68.5%	22.3%

Table 1: Types of left behind by gender (MIDEQ Survey, 2020)

Left behind children whose fathers have migrated represent 68.5% of cases (467 children). This proportion is 22.3% (152 children) when both parents are migrating and 9.2% of cases (63 children) when the mothers are migrating. According to gender, 68.2% of boys have fathers who migrated against only 8.7% whose mothers migrated. In 23.1% of cases, both parents are in migration. For female children, the proportions are 68.8%, 9.8% and 21.4% respectively.

Type of left behind by age category

Age (Year)	Migrants			Total
	Mother	Father	Both Parents	
5	5%	12%	5%	9%
6	13%	10%	6%	10%
7	13%	13%	11%	13%
8	4%	9%	10%	8%
9	6%	8%	7%	8%
10	11%	9%	12%	10%
11	5%	8%	4%	6%
12	6%	7%	14%	9%
13	11%	9%	7%	9%
14	8%	4%	5%	5%
15	3%	5%	6%	5%
16	5%	3%	4%	3%
17	10%	3%	9%	5%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 2: Type of left behind by age category (MIDEQ Survey, 2020)

Among those left behind, those aged 7 stand out the most, followed by children aged 6 and 10. In terms of proportion, 13% of children are 7 years old, 10% of cases are both 6 and 10 years old and 3% of children are 16 years old.

Schooling by type of left behind

High level of education	Migrants			Total
	Mother	Father	Both Parents	
None	59%	92%	76%	84%
Primary	41%	8%	24%	15%
Secondary	0%	1%	0%	1%
Higher education	0%	0%	0%	0%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 3: Types left behind by education level (MIDEQ Survey, 2020)

The level of education varies according to the type of left behind. Many of them have no education (84%). A total of 15% have primary education. Only 1% have secondary education. Above are the proportions according to the type of left behind. It can be seen that 41% of children left-behind by mother have primary education as opposed to 59% who have no education. Furthermore, 92% of children left-behind by father have no education, while 8% have primary education and 1% have secondary education. As for the children left-behind of both parents, 76% have no education compared to 24% with primary education.

Interruption of schooling by type of child

Chart 1: Interruption of schooling by type of child

The level of school interruption is generally low among children left behind (5.4%).

Interruption of schooling by migratory status of parents

Chart 2: Interruption of schooling by migratory status of parents

It can be seen that the level of interruption is highest among children whose mother is a migrant (19.1%), compared with around 4% if the father or both parents are migrants.

Type of school attended according to parents' migration status

Chart 3: Type of school attended according to parents' migration status

The proportion of children whose father is a migrant and who attend a public school is higher (64.6%) than that of children who have both parents (25.7%) or their mother (9.7%) in migration.

Type of school attended by left behind by gender

Chart 4: Type of school attended by left behind by gender

The proportion of left behind children attending public schools is higher than that of left behind children attending private and religious schools. By gender, 88% of males versus 86% of females attend the public school type. We can see that female left behind children attend more private schools, i.e. a proportion of 10% of all female left behind children compared to 1% of males.

Household characteristics and the schooling of the left behind

Residence of the head of household

The place of residence of the head of the household seems to have an impact on the schooling of children in general, and more specifically on the children left behind. We note that more than half of the children left behind we met live in rural areas in the context of migration in the Burkina-Ivory Coast corridor. That is to say, 89% of cases in rural areas against 11% in urban areas. The high rate of children left behind with primary education (90%) in rural areas compared to urban areas (10%) can be justified by this. The relationship between the place of residence of the head of household and the schooling of left behind children is significant at the 5% level.

Gender of the head of the household

The gender of the head of the household is thought to be associated with the schooling of children. In the Burkina Faso-Ivory Coast corridor, 74% of children left behind come from households headed by men, compared to 26% of children where the head of the household is a

woman. The number of children with primary school education who belong to a male-headed household is higher than that of a female-headed household, 73% versus 27% respectively. The above results can be explained by the source of income, which is mainly based on agriculture. It is noted that women have less access to land than men who are more often landowners. This state of affairs can lead to differences in income depending on the gender of the head of the household. It should be noted that the relationship between the schooling of the children of migrants who have remained in the country of origin and the gender of the head of the household is not significant at the 5% threshold.

Age of the head of the household of the left behind

The age of the head of the household to which the child belongs could be linked to the schooling of left behind children due to the migration of the child's biological parents to Ivory Coast. The majority of the heads of the households to which the children left behind belong are between 30 and 49 years old. It should be noted that 40% of the children left behind who have secondary education come from households where the age of the head of the household is between 30 and 49 years. The age of the head of the household to which the left behind children belong has a significant influence on the schooling of the left behind. At the 5% level, the relationship between the age of the head of the household to which the children belong, and the schooling of these children is significant.

Marital status of the head of the left-behind household

The marital status of the head of household affects children's school attendance. With regard to the schooling of left behind children, we can see that 81% of the left behind come from households that live in cohabitation, followed by 9% of cases that belong to households with a widowed marital status and 6% of cases where the head of the household has a single status. We note that among the left behind who have a primary level of education, 85% are from households that live in cohabitation and 70% of cases with a secondary level of education. There is a significant relationship at the 5% level between the two variables.

Religion of the head of the household to which the left behind belongs

In the context of migration between the Burkina-Ivory Coast corridor, this seems to have an impact, i.e. the religion of the head of the household to which the left behind belongs has an effect on the schooling of the left behind. We note that 40% of the left behind belong to households where the head of household is Muslim, 30% of cases where the head of household practices a traditional religion and 30% of the left behind are under the control of the head of household who is Christian. It is still found that 41% of the left behind at the primary level are from households that practice the Muslim religion and 46% of the cases at the secondary level. The relationship between these two variables is significant at the 5% level.

Place of birth of the head of the left-behind household

The place of birth seems to be related to schooling. People are easily influenced by their environment. Being born and growing up in an environment could undoubtedly leave traces in one's life. Let's see how to understand this in the context of migration. From the analysis of the data, we can see that 94% of the left-behind cases identified are from households whose head of household was born in Burkina Faso and 6% of cases are from households whose head of household was born in Ivory Coast. The relationship between the level of education and the place of birth is significant at the 5% threshold.

Main occupation of the head of the household of the left behind

The relationship between the main occupation of the head of the household to which the left behind belongs and the schooling of the left behind is not very direct. The latter are more likely

to attend school in households where the head has a stable job. We note that more than half (85%) of the children left behind come from households where the head of the household's main occupation is agriculture, followed by 5% of cases where the head of the household is a vendor (trader). Of all the children left behind who have a primary level of education, 86% of cases come from households where the head of the household is a farmer and 5% of cases where the head of the household is a vendor. At the secondary level, 69% of the left behind are from households headed by farmers and 6% are from households headed by vendors. The relationship between the main occupation of the head of the household to which the children left behind belong and their schooling is significant at the 5% level.

Size of the household to which the left behind belongs

The size of the household in many situations is an explanatory factor of the life that household members lead. What about in the context of migration between the Burkina-Ivory Coast corridors? After analysis, it can be seen that half of the children left behind (50%) identified come from households between [2-10], followed by 35% of cases whose household size is between [10-20] and 7% of cases whose household size is between [20-30]. We also note that 54% of children left behind at secondary level come from households between [10- 20] compared to 49% at primary level. For households between [20- 30], 8% of children left behind were primary school children compared to 6% of secondary school children.

Monthly income of the left-behind household

Income could explain the schooling status of a child. The results of the survey show that 34% of the children left behind come from households with an income of 0 - 19,999 XOF, 19% of cases come from households with an income of 20,000 - 39,999 XOF, 17% of the left behind have an income of 40,000 - 69, 999 XOF, and 12% of cases have an income of 70,000 - 119,999 XOF. We have 33% of the children left behind at primary level and 18% of those left behind at secondary level, all from households with an income of between 0 - 19,999 XOF. For an income between 40,000 - 69,999 XOF, we have 24% of secondary level left behind against 18% of primary level cases.

Multiple Correspondence Analysis

Chart 4: Variables representation of Multiple Correspondence Analysis

Based on the contribution of different variables on the axes, the factorial map of the variables shows that the place of birth of the head of the household, the place of residence, the monthly income of the household, the age of the head of the household, the marital status and the main occupation of the head of the household to which the left behind belong are factors that influence the schooling of the children left behind. In order of importance, based on the contribution of the various factors on the dimensions, it emerges that the main occupation, the area of residence, age and marital status are the factors that most influence the level of schooling of children left behind in the context of migration in the Burkina Faso-Ivory Coast corridor.

DISCUSSION

There are many characteristics of the households of children left behind that can have an impact on the schooling of these children. To this end, a number of characteristics of the households to which the child left behind belongs were examined. The results show that, at the 5% risk, there is a statistically significant association between the schooling of children left behind and household characteristics such as place of birth, religion, main occupation, age, marital status, place of residence of the head of household and the monthly income of the household to which the child belongs.

About the marital status of the head of household, relating to monogamous versus polygamous households, monogamous heads of household enrol their children in school more than polygamous heads of household (M. PILON, 1993 p. 85; D. NGANAWARA, 2016, p. 26). The works dealing with the link between religion and schooling in Africa reveals the complexity of this relationship, which generally leads to diverse situations depending on the context. The attitude of families towards the education of their children is essentially directed by the desire to transmit a set of values that they hold, and acceptance of school is not necessarily the same for populations of different religious affiliations (M. H. DURAND, 2006 p. 12).

The relationship between the main occupation of the head of the household to which the left behind belongs and the schooling of the left behind is not very direct. From J. P. LACHAUD (2007, p. 9) point of view, the influence of activity status is said to be mediated by the income of the head of household, which depends on the latter's activity and allows households to improve their living conditions and invest in the human capital of their children

It should be noted that the gender of the head of the household to which the children left behind migrate in the Burkina Faso-Ivory Coast corridor is not a factor influencing the level of schooling of the children left behind, as it is in the studies conducted on children by R. BARROS et al. (1997 p. 253) in Latin America. This could be justified by the fact that very often the child is more afraid of his or her biological parents than others. In a situation of parental migration, being left behind, the children would be in a situation of less affection. With the exception of numerous studies (P. DE VREYER, 1993, p. 63; D. CLEVENOT & M. PILON, 1996 p. 2; J. F. KOBIANÉ, 2003 p. 23; C. B. LLOYD & A. K. BLANC 1996 p. 267; J. WAKAM, 2002, p. 1) carried out in sub-Saharan Africa, which reveal that children living in female-headed households are far better educated than those living in male-headed households and that female under-education is less.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of this article was to explore the link between household characteristics and the schooling of children left behind and to identify the socio-demographic characteristics of children's households that could influence the schooling of children left behind, using data from

the MIDEQ 2020 survey. Such an analysis is likely to help identify certain factors that can facilitate decision making for decision-makers and guide their actions with regard to the schooling of children in general and those left behind in particular, in the context of migration between the Burkina - Ivory Coast corridor. Although progress has been made in recent years to reduce child-related inequalities in the context of migration, these inequalities are still significant. The results of the differential analysis reveal that the socio-demographic characteristics of households except the gender of the head of the household and the size of the household influence the schooling of children left behind due to the migration of the child's biological parents from Burkina Faso to Ivory Coast. These results call on decision-makers, the parents of children left behind and the households to which these children belong to pay particular attention to the right to education of children in general and those in a migration situation in particular. This could contribute on the one hand to the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal 4 "to ensure equal access to quality education for all and to promote equal learning opportunities throughout life" and on the other hand to improve school performance, which is less explored in the present study.

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INSTRUCTIONS AUX AUTEURS

1- Contexte, Justification et Objectifs du journal

Le développement des territoires ruraux est une préoccupation prise en compte par de nombreux organismes internationaux que nationaux à travers les projets et programmes de développement.

En Afrique, le défi du développement est indissociable du devenir des espaces ruraux. Les territoires ruraux sont caractérisés par d'importantes activités rurales qui influencent sur la dynamique du monde rural et la restructuration des espaces ruraux.

En effet, de profondes mutations s'observent de plus en plus au sein du monde rural à travers les activités agricoles et extra agricoles. Des innovations s'insèrent dans les habitudes traditionnelles des ruraux. Cela affecte sans doute le système de production des biens et services et les relations entre les villes et campagnes.

Ainsi, dans ce contexte de mutation sociétale, de nouvelles formes d'organisation spatiale s'opèrent. Ces nouvelles formes dénotent en partie par les différents modes de faire-valoir. Aussi, plusieurs composantes environnementales sont-elles impactées et nécessitent donc une attention particulière qui interpelle aussi bien les dirigeants politiques, les organismes non étatiques et les populations locales pour une gestion durable des espaces ruraux.

Par ailleurs, le contexte de la décentralisation, le développement à la base implique toutes les couches sociales afin d'amorcer réellement le développement. Ainsi, la femme rurale, à travers le rôle qu'elle joue dans le système de production de biens et services, mérite une attention particulière sur le plan formation, information et place dans la société en pleine mutation.

Enfin, en analysant le contexte socioculturel et l'évolution de la croissance démographique que connaissent les campagnes, les questions d'assainissement en milieu rural doivent de plus en plus faire l'objet des préoccupations majeures à tous les niveaux de prises de décision afin de garantir à tous un cadre de vie sain et réduire l'extrême pauvreté en milieu rural.

Le premier numéro du Journal de Géographie Rurale Appliquée et Développement (*J_GRAD*) du Laboratoire de Géographie Rurale et d'Expertise Agricole (LaGREA) s'inscrit dans la logique de parcourir de façon profonde tous les aspects liés au monde rural. A ce titre, les axes thématiques prioritaires ci-après seront explorés.

Axe 1 : Dynamique des espaces ruraux et Aménagement de l'espace rural

- ✓ Mutations spatiales et dynamique des espaces ruraux ;
- ✓ Gestion du foncier rural et environnementale ;
- ✓ Climat, aménagements hydroagricoles ;
- ✓ SIG et gestion des territoires ruraux ;
- ✓ Gouvernance et planification des espaces ruraux.

Axe 2 : Economie rurale

- ✓ Activités agricoles et sécurité alimentaire ;
- ✓ Ecotourisme ;
- ✓ Artisanat rural ;
- ✓ Territoires, mobilité et cultures.

Axe 3 : Genre et développement rural

- ✓ Femmes et activités rurales ;
- ✓ Développement local ;
- ✓ Echanges transfrontaliers dans les espaces ruraux ;
- ✓ Hygiène et assainissement en milieu rural.

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Le Journal de Géographie Rurale Appliquée et Développement (*J_GRAD*) publie des contributions originales en français ou en anglais dans tous les domaines de la science sociale.

Les contributions publiées par le journal représentent l'opinion des auteurs et non celle du comité de rédaction. Tous les auteurs sont considérés comme responsables de la totalité du contenu de leurs contributions.

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Le manuscrit à soumettre au journal doit être original et n'ayant jamais été fait objet de publication au paravent. Le manuscrit doit comporter les adresses postales et électroniques et le numéro de téléphone de l'auteur à qui doivent être adressées les correspondances. Ce manuscrit soumis au journal doit impérativement respecter les exigences du journal.

La période de soumission des manuscrits est de : 10 août au 10 septembre 2022.

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La première page doit comporter le titre de l'article, les noms des auteurs, leur institution d'affiliation et leur adresse complète. Elle devra comporter également un titre courant ne dépassant pas une soixantaine de caractères ainsi que l'adresse postale de l'auteur, à qui les correspondances doivent être adressées.

- Le titre de l'article est en corps 14, majuscule et centré avec un espace de 12 pts après le titre (format > paragraphe > espace après : 12 pts).
- Les noms et prénoms des auteurs doivent apparaître en corps 12, majuscule et centré et en italique.
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2.2.3. Résumé

Le résumé comporte de 250 à 300 mots et est présenté en Français et en Anglais. Il ne contient ni référence, ni tableau, ni figure et doit être lisible. Il doit obligatoirement être structuré en cinq parties ayant respectivement pour titres : « Description du sujet », « Objectifs », « Méthode », « Résultats » et « Conclusions ». Le résumé est accompagné d'au plus 05 mots-clés. Le résumé et les mots-clés sont composés en corps 9, en italique, en minuscule et justifiés.

2.2.4. Introduction

L'introduction doit fournir suffisamment d'informations de base, situant le contexte dans lequel l'étude a été réalisée. Elle doit permettre au lecteur de juger de l'étude et d'évaluer les résultats acquis.

2.2.5. Corps du sujet

Le corps du texte est structuré suivant le modèle IMReD. Chacune des parties joue un rôle précis. Elles représentent les étapes de la présentation.

2.2.5.1 Introduction

L'introduction doit indiquer le sujet et se référer à la littérature publiée. Elle doit présenter une question de recherche.

L'objectif de cette partie est de mettre en avant l'intérêt du travail qui est décrit dans l'article et de justifier le choix de la question de recherche et de la démarche scientifique.

2.2.5.2 Matériel et méthodes

Cette partie doit comprendre deux volets : présentation succincte du cadre de recherche et l'approche méthodologique adoptée.

2.2.5.3 Résultats

Les résultats sont présentés sous forme de figures, de tableaux et/ou de descriptions. Il n'y a pas d'interprétation des résultats dans cette partie. Il faut particulièrement veiller à ce qu'il n'y ait pas de redondance inutile entre le texte et les illustrations (tableaux ou figures) ou entre les illustrations elles-mêmes.

2.2.5.4 Discussion

La discussion met en rapport les résultats obtenus à ceux d'autres travaux de recherche. Dans cette partie, on peut rappeler l'originalité et l'intérêt de la recherche. A cet effet, il faut mettre en avant les conséquences pratiques qu'implique cette recherche. Il ne faut pas reprendre des éléments qui auraient leur place dans l'introduction.

2.2.6 Conclusion

Cette partie résume les principaux résultats et précise les questions qui attendent encore des réponses.

Les différentes parties du corps du sujet doivent apparaître dans un ordre logique.

L'ensemble du texte est en corps 12, minuscule, interligne simple, sans césure dans le texte, avec un alinéa de première ligne de 5 mm et justifié (Format > paragraphe > retrait > 1ère ligne > positif > 0,5 cm). Un espace de 6 pts est défini après chaque paragraphe (format > paragraphe > espace après : 6 pts). Les marges (haut, bas, gauche et droite) sont de 2,5 cm.

- Les titres (des parties) sont alignés à gauche, sans alinéa et en numérotation décimale
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La rédaction doit être faite dans un style simple et concis, avec des phrases courtes, en évitant les répétitions.

2.2.8. Remerciements

Les remerciements au personnel d'assistance ou à des supports financiers devront être adressés en terme concis.

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Les passages cités sont présentés en romain et entre guillemets. Lorsque la phrase citant et la citation dépassent trois lignes, il faut aller à la ligne, pour présenter la citation (interligne 1) en romain, en diminuant la taille de police d'un point. Les références de citation sont intégrées au texte citant, selon les cas, des façons suivantes :

- (Initiale(s) du Prénom ou des Prénoms de l'Auteur, année de publication, pages citées);

Exemples :

1-Selon C. Mathieu (1987, p. 139) aucune amélioration agricole ne peut être réalisée sans le plein accord des communautés locales et sans une base scientifique bien éprouvée ;

2-L'autre importance des activités non agricoles, c'est qu'elles permettent de sortir les paysans du cycle de dépendance dans laquelle enferment les aléas de la pluviométrie (M. Gueye, 2010, p. 21) ;

3-K. F. Yao *et al.*, (2018, p.127), estime que le conflit foncier intervient également dans les cas d'imprécision ou de violation des limites de la parcelle à mettre en valeur. Cette violation des limites de parcelles concédées engendre des empiètements et des installations d'autres migrants parfois à l'issue du donateur.

Les sources historiques, les références d'informations orales et les notes explicatives sont numérotées en série continue et présentées en bas de page. Les divers éléments d'une référence bibliographique sont présentés comme suit :

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FANGNON Bernard, 2012, *Qualité des sols, systèmes de production agricole et impacts environnementaux et socioéconomiques dans le Département du Couffo au sud-ouest du Bénin*. Thèse de Doctorat en Géographie, EDP/FLASH/UAC, p.308

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